

Speculation on Scaling, Maximum Entropy and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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We consider the case of a mass, m_0 , at rest and suggest that the idea of time applies to it because there could be a probability for the mass to decay, emit a particle etc. at any instant. We further suggest that if scaling applies, i.e. if one doubles the rest mass, one doubles the probability for such a decay and halves the frequency. This leads to the notion of a frequency $1/(m_0 b)$ where b is a constant to allow for proper units to arise. Scaling, however, seems to be linked to maximum entropy in the sense that m_0 is proportional to the probability to decay.

The above rest mass, however, may be observed from a frame moving with a constant $-v$. In such a case, it maps to $E(m_0, v)$ =energy and $p(m_0, v)$, momentum. The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ with its degeneracies $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ gives exactly the frequency proportional to $1/(m_0 b)$ in the case of $v=0$. Thus, we suggest that an inherent scaling feature of m_0 at rest carries over into a scenario with E and p and serves as the root for $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction.

The Notion of Scaling

Classical mechanics considers the probability:

$P(x)dx = dx/L$ where L is an arbitrary length ((1)).

((1)) holds for any velocity v , energy E and momentum p . In other words, these properties are not distinguished in the probability. A quantum free particle probability (wavefunction), $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, does distinguish on the basis of E and p . We try to consider how this may possibly come about.

The Scenario of a Mass at Rest

We consider a mass, m_0 , at rest with an external clock ticking. If this clock is removed and there are no external interactions with m_0 , one may ask: Is there still the notion of time? We suggest that time still exists because a rest mass, m_0 , may decay, i.e. have internal interactions. We further suggest that such a decay is probabilistic and introduce the notion of scaling. If a rest mass, m_0 , has a probability P_1 to decay, then $2m_0$ has a probability of $2P_1$ to decay. This leads to a decay frequency of:

$1/(m_0 b)$ where b is a constant to create proper units. ((2))

Thus, there is a kind of time interval appearing which is proportional to $1/m_0$.

Special Relativity

According to special relativity, a rest mass may be viewed from a frame moving with constant velocity $-v$. In such a case, a rest mass is represented by an energy, $E(m_0, v)$, and momentum, $p(m_0, v)$ such that:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((3))$$

We have discussed in previous notes the degenerate A values for:

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E \quad ((4b)) \quad n = \text{integer}$$

Here we note that if $v=0$, then $\hbar/E = \hbar/(m_0 c^2)$ ((5))

((5)) is the rest mass frequency discussed above. Thus, we argue that the notion of \hbar/E as a time resolution and \hbar/p as a spatial one have their root in a mass at rest, m_0 , which has a probability to decay proportional to m_0 . As noted, this leads to a frequency proportional to $1/m_0$.

Entropy Considerations

We suggest that the above arguments pertaining to m_0 are linked with maximum entropy. In other words, one considers the probability for decay to be proportional to rest mass m_0 . Doubling the rest mass doubles the probability. This is like the notion of the number of states in a volume V being proportional to the volume. If one doubles the volume, one doubles the number of states.

As a result, we argue that the scaling notion is equivalent to the idea of maximum entropy and this, in turn, leads to frequency to decay proportional to $1/m_0$. This frequency, however, may be considered to be clock gradation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one considers that a rest mass, m_0 , may decay and so inherently contains the notion of time and further argues that this decay is probabilistic with maximum entropy, then scaling should apply. In other words, if P_1 is the probability for a decay to occur in m_0 , the $2P_1$ is the probability for $2m_0$. This suggests that $2m_0$ has $1/2$ the frequency, so we suggest a frequency proportional to $1/(m_0 c^2)$ where c is a constant which yields proper units.

Special relativity shows that a rest m_0 has energy, $E(m_0, v)$, and momentum, $p(m_0, v)$, when seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$. The Lorentz invariant, $A = -Et + px$, also holds and has degeneracies, $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$, where n is an integer. If $v=0$, then the time interval $n \cdot \hbar/E$ becomes $1/(m_0 c^2)$ which is the value discussed above. Thus, we suggest that the root of a time resolution of \hbar/E and a spatial resolution of \hbar/p comes ultimately from a rest mass, m_0 , which is proportional to the probability for it to decay, leading to a frequency proportional to $1/m_0$. Such a scaling approach, we argue, is equivalent to maximization of

entropy because we assume no knowledge of the decay process and assume that doubling the rest mass doubles the decay probability.